

**CASE COMMENT: LEGALITY OF THE THREAT OR USE OF
NUCLEAR WEAPONS, ADVISORY OPINION, ICJ REPORTS, 1996
(CASE ANALYSIS)**

by

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Abstract

In the recent scenario of world politics, the change in geopolitics, international alliances and the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war, there have been threats of using nuclear weapons to maintain the supremacy and hegemony in front of the world. However, what has missed everyone's sight is the gravity of those weapons that don't just threaten a particular country, or a camp in an international alliance, it threatens all of us in the basis of humanity. It threatens to wipe our existence. This case comment is an attempt to analyse the landmark judgement of International Court of Justice with respect to the use or threat of use of nuclear weapons and the impact of this judgement in the times to come.

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Facts

A request made by the General Assembly of the United Nations on the question concerning the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons by the International Court of Justice.

Court Composition:

President Bedjaoui, Vice-President Schwebel; Judges Oda, Guillaume, Shahabuddeen, Weeramantry, Ranjeva, Herczegh, Shi, Fleischhauer, Koroma, Vereshchetin, Ferrari Bravo, Higgins; Registrar Valencia-Ospina.

Issues

The primary questions of law raised in front of the Court were as follows:

1. Jurisdiction & Discretion of the Court

- 1.1 Whether it has the jurisdiction to give a reply to the request of the General Assembly for an advisory opinion?
- 1.2 Whether or not the Court will give an advisory opinion that has been requested of it and whether the answer should be in affirmative or is there any reason to decline the exercise of such jurisdiction?

2. Applicability of Law

Whether a signalled intention to use force if certain events occur is or is not a "threat" within Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter depends upon various factors?

3. Rules on the lawfulness or unlawfulness of nuclear weapons as such

- 3.1. Whether there are specific rules in international law regulating the legality of- illegality of recourse to nuclear weapons per se?
- 3.2. Whether a prohibition of the threat or use of nuclear weapons as such flows from customary source of law?
- 3.3. Whether recourse to nuclear weapons must be considered as illegal in the light of the principles and rules of international humanitarian law applicable in armed conflict and of the law of neutrality?

3.4. Whether the threat or use of nuclear weapons would be lawful or unlawful in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which the very survival of a State would be at stake?

Rationale

1. Jurisdiction of the Court

1.1 Whether it has the jurisdiction to give a reply to the request of the General Assembly for an advisory opinion?

A: The Court observed that it draws its competence in respect of advisory opinions from Article 65, paragraph 1, of its Statute. Along with this, as per Article 96, paragraph 1, of the Charter of UN provides that the advisory opinion may be requested by the General Assembly or the Security Council on any legal question.

However, on this some opposing States argued that the General Assembly and the Security Council may ask for an advisory opinion on any legal question only within the scope of their activities. In the view of the court, the General Assembly had competence in any event to seise the court.

The Court also refereed to Articles 10, 11 and 13 of the Charter and concluded relevance to many aspects of the activities and concerns of the General Assembly, including those relating to the threat or use of force in international relations, the disarmament process and the progressive developments of International Law.

1.2 Whether or not the Court will give an advisory opinion that has been requested of it & whether the answer should be in affirmative or is there any reason to decline the exercise of such jurisdiction?

A: The Court observed that the Statute leaves discretion as to the option of rendering an advisory opinion once it has established the competence to do. With reference to Article 65, paragraph 1, it was observed that it is an enabling provision for the Court to do so.

The court, while quoting *Interpretation of Peace Treaties with Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania, First Phase, Advisory Opinion, ICJ Reports 1950*, also noted that its opinion is not given to the states but to the organ which is entitled to request it.

Several reasons were adduced in these proceedings in order to persuade the Court that in the exercise of its discretionary power it should decline to render the opinion requested by the General Assembly. Some states so contended that the question was vague and abstract and that there exists no specific dispute on the subject matter of the question and it might lead the court to make hypothetical or speculative declarations outside the scope of its judicial function.

The court then noted that the purpose of the advisory function isn't to settle at least directly disputes between states, but to offer legal advice to the organs and institutions requesting the opinion. The question of being a specific dispute thereby did not lead the court to decline rendering the advice.

The court did not accept those arguments concluded that it has the authority to deliver an opinion.

Held: By 13:1, decided to comply with the request for an advisory opinion.

2. Applicability of Law

Whether a signalled intention to use force if certain events occur is or is not a "threat" within Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter depends upon various factors?

A: In Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter, the use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of another State or in any other manner inconsistent with the purpose of the United Nations is prohibited. This prohibition of the use of force is to be considered in the light of other relevant provisions of the Charter.

In Article 51, the Charter recognizes the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence if an armed attack occurs. A further lawful use of force is envisaged in Article 42, whereby the Security Council may take military enforcement measures in conformity with Chapter VII of the Charter. These provisions do not refer to specific weapons. They apply to any use of force, regardless of the weapons employed.

The Charter neither expressly prohibits, nor permits, the use of any specific weapon, including nuclear weapons. The entitlement to resort to self-defence under Article 51 is subject to the conditions of necessity and proportionality. As the Court stated in the case concerning Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. United States of America)

(I. C. J. Reports 1986, p. 94, para. 176): "there is a specific rule whereby self-defence would warrant only measures which are proportionate to the armed attack and necessary to respond to it, a rule well established in customary international law".

The proportionality principle may thus not in itself exclude the use of nuclear weapons in self-defence in all circumstances. But at the same time, a use of force that is proportionate under the law of self-defence must, in order to be lawful, also meet the requirements of the law applicable in armed conflict, which comprise in particular the principles and rules of humanitarian law. And the Court notes that the very nature of all nuclear weapons and the profound risks associated therewith are further considerations to be borne in mind by States believing they can exercise a nuclear response in self-defence in accordance with the requirements of proportionality.

In order to lessen or eliminate the risk of unlawful attack, States sometimes signal that they possess certain weapons to use in self-defence against any State violating their territorial integrity or political independence. Whether a signalled intention to use force if certain events occur is or is not a "threat" within Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter depends upon various factors.

The notions of "threat" and "use" of force under Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter stand together in the sense that if the use of force itself in a given case is illegal-for whatever reason-the threat to use such force will likewise be illegal. In short, if it is to be lawful, the declared readiness of a State to use force must be a use of force that is in conformity with the Charter.

Held: Unanimously, A threat or use of force by means of nuclear weapons that is contrary to Article 2, paragraph 4, of the Charter of the United Nations and that fails to meet all the requirements of Article 5 1 is unlawful.

3. Rules on the lawfulness or unlawfulness of nuclear weapons as such

3.1. Whether there are specific rules in international law regulating or authorising the legality or illegality of recourse to nuclear weapons per se?

A: The Court noted by way of introduction that international customary and treaty law does not contain any specific prescription authorizing the threat or use of nuclear weapons or any other weapon in general or in certain circumstances, in particular those of the exercise of legitimate self-defence. Nor, however, is there any principle or rule of international law which

would make the legality of the threat or use of nuclear weapons or of any other weapons dependent on a specific authorization. State practice shows that the illegality of the use of certain weapons as such does not result from an absence of authorization but, on the contrary, is formulated in terms of prohibition

It does not seem to the Court that the use of nuclear weapons can be regarded as specifically prohibited on the basis of certain provisions of the Second Hague Declaration of 1899, the Regulations annexed to the Hague Convention IV of 1907 or the 1925 Geneva Protocol. The pattern until now has been for weapons of mass destruction to be declared illegal by specific instruments. But the Court does not find any specific prohibition of recourse to nuclear weapons in treaties expressly prohibiting the use of certain weapons of mass destruction; and observes that, although, in the last two decades, a great many negotiations have been conducted regarding nuclear weapons, they have not resulted in a treaty of general prohibition of the same kind as for bacteriological and chemical weapons.

Held: Unanimously, there is in neither customary nor conventional international law any specific authorization of the threat or use of nuclear weapons

3.2. Whether a prohibition of the threat or use of nuclear weapons as such flows from customary source of law?

A: It notes that the members of the international community are profoundly divided on the matter of whether non-recourse to nuclear weapons over the past 50 years constitutes the expression of an *opinio juris*. Under these circumstances the Court does not consider itself able to find that there is such an *opinio juris*. It points out that the adoption each year by the General Assembly, by a large majority, of resolutions recalling the content of Resolution 1653 (XVI), and requesting the Member States to conclude a convention prohibiting the use of nuclear weapons in any circumstance, reveals the desire of a very large section of the international community to take, by a specific and express prohibition of the use of nuclear weapons, a significant step forward along the road to complete nuclear disarmament.

The emergence, as *lex lata*, of a customary rule specifically prohibiting the use of nuclear weapons as such is hampered by the continuing tensions between the nascent *opinio juris*, on the one hand, and the still strong adherence to the doctrine of deterrence (in which the right to use those weapons in the exercise of the right to self-defence against an armed attack threatening the vital security interests of the State is reserved), on the other.

Held: By 11:3, there is in neither customary nor conventional international law any comprehensive and universal prohibition of the threat or use of nuclear weapons as such

3.3. Whether recourse to nuclear weapons must be considered as illegal in the light of the principles and rules of international humanitarian law applicable in armed conflict and of the law of neutrality?

A: After sketching the historical development of the body of rules which originally were called "laws and customs of war" and later came to be termed "international humanitarian law", the Court observes that the cardinal principles contained in the texts constituting the fabric of humanitarian law, protection of the civilian population and civilian objects, civilians not being the object of attack and never using weapons incapable of distinguishing between civilian and military targets by the State. Also, it is prohibited to cause unnecessary suffering to combatants: it is accordingly prohibited to use weapons causing them such harm or uselessly aggravating their suffering. In application of that second principle, States do not have unlimited freedom of choice of means in the weapons they use.

The Court also referred to the Martens Clause, which was first included in the Hague Convention II with respect to the Laws and Customs of War on Land of 1899 and which has proved to be an effective means of addressing the rapid evolution of military technology.

The Court noted that nuclear weapons were invented after most of the principles and rules of humanitarian law applicable in armed conflict had already come into existence; the Conferences of 1949 and 1974-1977 left these weapons aside, and there is a qualitative as well as quantitative difference between nuclear weapons and all conventional arms. However, in the Court's view, it couldn't be concluded from this that the established principles and rules of humanitarian law applicable in armed conflict did not apply to nuclear weapons. Such a conclusion would be incompatible with the intrinsically humanitarian character of the legal principles in question which permeates the entire law of armed conflict and applies to all forms of warfare and to all kinds of weapons, those of the past, those of the present and those of the future.

Held: Unanimously, A threat or use of nuclear weapons should also be compatible with the requirements of the international law applicable in armed conflict, particularly those of the principles and rules of international humanitarian law, as well as with specific obligations under treaties and other undertakings which expressly deal with nuclear weapons

3.4. Whether the threat or use of nuclear weapons would be lawful or unlawful in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which the very survival of a State would be at stake?

A: The Court observed that, in view of the unique characteristics of nuclear weapons, to which the Court has referred above, the use of such weapons in fact seems scarcely reconcilable with respect for the requirements of the law applicable in armed conflict. It considers, nevertheless, that it does not have sufficient elements to enable it to conclude with certainty that the use of nuclear weapons would necessarily be at variance with the principles and rules of law applicable in armed conflict in any circumstance.

Furthermore, the Court couldn't lose sight of the fundamental right of every State to survival, and thus its right to resort to self-defence, in accordance with Article 51 of the Charter, when its survival is at stake. Nor could it ignore the practice referred to as "policy of deterrence", to which an appreciable section of the international community adhered for many years. Accordingly, in view of the present state of international law viewed as a whole, as examined by the Court, and of the elements of fact at its disposal, the Court is led to observe that it could not reach a definitive conclusion as to the legality or illegality of the use of nuclear weapons by a State in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which its very survival would be at stake.

Held: By 7:7, in view of the current state of international law, and of the elements of fact at its disposal, the Court cannot conclude definitively whether the threat or use of nuclear weapons would be lawful or unlawful in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which the very survival of a State would be at stake.

There exists an obligation to pursue in good faith and bring to a conclusion, negotiations leading to nuclear disarmament in all its aspects under strict and effective international control.

Analysis

With the opportunity to critically analyse the advisory opinion that has been rendered by the ICJ, in my opinion, the Hon'ble court missed out on an opportunity to take a firmer stand on the threat or use of nuclear weapons that can endanger the whole of humanity even when the existence of a State could be in danger.

The world has not recovered from the nuclear bombings at Hiroshima and Nagasaki till today, the humanity isn't done paying its price even for being innocent, and losing all their life and livelihood. However, it is to be emphasised that for the first time, the Court unambiguously stated that the use or threat of use of nuclear weapons is contrary to the rules of international law applicable, inter alia, to armed conflict and, more particularly, to the principles and rules of humanitarian law as supported by the separate opinion of Judge Ranjeva.

As opined from the dissenting opinion of Vice-President Schwebel, when it comes to the supreme interests of State, the Court discards the legal progress of the twentieth century, puts aside the provisions of the Charter of the United Nations of which it is 'the principal judicial organ', and proclaims, in terms redolent of Realpolitik, its ambivalence about the most important provisions of modern international law.

The gravity of possessing nuclear weapons is unrealised, for decades after its use they induce health related problems, cause congenital deformities, mental retardation and genetic damage; have the potential to cause a nuclear winter; contaminate and destroy the food chain; imperil the ecosystem, produce social disintegration; imperil all civilization; threaten human survival, and wreck cultural devastation. And all these consequences are not unseen, the world has been a witness to this suffering once.

Nuclear weapons have the potential to wipe out the entire existence of humanity, so isn't that a threat persisting on all of us regardless of the boundaries of States that exist as opposed to the argument of the Court to being unsure about the self defence of a State. While writing a declaration, President Bedjaoui considered that "self-defence-if exercised under extreme circumstances in which the very survival of a State is in question-cannot engender a situation in which a State would exonerate itself from compliance with the 'intransgressible' norms of international humanitarian law".

Vice-President Schwebel concurred to this view and said, "But it cannot be accepted that the use of nuclear weapons on a scale which would--or could--result in the deaths of "many millions in indiscriminate inferno and by far-reaching fallout . . . and render uninhabitable much or all of the earth, could be lawful." According to him, it would be very rash to accord, without any hesitation, a higher priority to the survival of a State than to the survival of humanity itself.

However, Judge Fleischhauer's separate opinion highlights that international law has not yet overcome the dichotomy that is created by the very existence of nuclear weapons between the law applicable in armed conflict, and in particular the rules and principles of humanitarian law,

on the one side, and the inherent right of self defence, on the other. The separate opinion continues that the Court could and should have gone further in order to reconcile the conflicting principles. I second the opinion of the Hon'ble Judge.

As the legal question in the judgement was tied by 7:7, one of the salient standpoint was of Judge Weeramantry's, who proposed that use or threat of use of nuclear weapons is illegal in any circumstances whatsoever.

It violates the fundamental principles of international law, and represents the very negation of the humanitarian concerns which underlie the structure of humanitarian law. It offends conventional law and, in particular, the Geneva Gas Protocol of 1925 and article 23 (a) of the Hague Regulations of 1907 as they prohibit the use of poison. Radiation fell directly within this description, and the prohibition against the use of poisons was indeed one of the oldest rules of the laws of war.

It contradicts the fundamental principle of the dignity and worth of the human person on which all law depends. It endangers the human environment in a manner which threatens the entirety of life on the planet.

Concludingly, Judge Weeramantry's opinion drew attention to the multicultural and ancient origins of the laws of war, referring to the recognition of it, basic rules in Hindu, Buddhist, Chinese, Judaic, Islamic, African and modern European cultural traditions.

As such, the humanitarian rules of warfare were not to be regarded as a new sentiment, invented in the nineteenth century, and so slenderly rooted in universal tradition that they may be lightly overridden. There cannot be two sets of the laws of war applicable simultaneously to the same conflict--one to conventional weapons, and the other to nuclear weapons.

However, concludingly the question of threat or use of nuclear weapons in the exercise of self defence recognised by Article 51 of the UN Charter, divided the Quorum into half which could be considered as a half win, to say, for the humanity.

Conclusion

Concludingly, the decision taken by the Court was significant in ensuring the responsible use of nuclear weapons and to prohibit it until the need for self defence. However, in my opinion,

there should have been an effort to reconcile the principles of International Humanitarian Law with the same.

The need to restrain brutalities the dictates of the conscience of humanity. Law essentially implies comparisons in which humanitarian considerations have to be weighed against military requirements. Thus, the collateral damage caused to the civilian population must not be 'excessive' as compared to the "military advantage" offered which was aptly opined by the Court.

However, nuclear weapons, when used are incapable of distinguishing between civilians and military personnel, and would result in the death of thousands if not millions of civilians, cause stated that superfluous injury and unnecessary suffering to survivors, affect future generations, damage hospitals and contaminate the natural environment, food and drinking water with radioactivity, thereby depriving survivors of the means of survival, contrary to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and weapons would be lawful or unlawful in an extreme the 1977 Additional Protocol I thereto.

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